

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF CONJUNCTIONS, DISJUNCTIONS AND PREPOSITIONS IN THE FORMATION OF STYLISTIC DEVICES

Javid Babayev

*Senior lecturer of the chair "English and methods"
Nakhchivan State University*

Abstract

The article elaborates the role and function of conjunctions, disjunctions and prepositions in the formation of some rhetoric devices. Conjunctions such as 'neither...nor', 'either...or', 'or', 'and', 'no...or', 'like', 'as', as well as some prepositions are capable of creating a number of stylistic devices. Even the omissions of these conjunctions result in emergence of a new rhetoric device. Paradiastole, asyndeton, polysyndeton, meiosis, hyperbole, simile are produced as a result of usage of the afore-mentioned conjunctions, disjunctions and prepositions. It has been noted that excessive use of conjunction 'and' makes polysyndeton while normal usage of this conjunction is called "syndeton". However, the deliberate omission of any conjunctions is characterized as "asyndeton". Conjunctions as "like" and "as" are used to produce meiosis, hyperbole and simile. Excessive use of any conjunction leads to pleonasm which is the sign of hackneyed or trite language. The article revealed the difference between conjunctions and disjunctions. The author underlines that disjunctions should be categorized as a separate part of speech in grammar. This claim is one of the novelties of English grammar, as well.

Keywords: stylistic devices, paradiastole, polysyndeton, asyndeton, syndeton, simile, meiosis, hyperbole, pleonasm

Introduction. The article scrutinizes the stylistic opportunities of conjunctions, disjunctions and prepositions. As notional parts of speech, functional parts of speech also have the function to create some stylistic devices and means. Conjunctions are one of the functional parts of speech which can form some stylistic means or devices. Conjunctions can easily create paradiastole, polysyndeton. Sometimes, it is possible to come across the deliberate omission of conjunctions which is called asyndeton in stylistics. The so-called conjunctions are usually used in syntactical stylistic devices. Structurally, conjunctions used to form a syntactical stylistic device can be coordinating, correlative, subordinating. Disjunctive conjunctions as 'or' or 'neither...nor', 'no...or' should be classified as disjunctions and given a special status as another functional part of speech. From logical point of view, a word which has the function of disjunction cannot be conjunctive. Since conjunctive words serve to join two or words or sentences. However, disjunctive words are known to separate the words or sentences. Therefore, disjunctions should be classified as a separate part of speech in grammar. Sometimes, we can see "disjunctive conjunction" in some grammar rules which generates "oxymoron" in any sense. When we approach the

issue from linguistic point of view, we also witness two contradictory meanings used side by side which is inappropriate as well.

Paradiastole is observed with the usage of disjunctions such as 'neither...nor', 'no...or', 'not either...or', 'either...or'. Disjunction does not mean that we should always use negation. The main essence in disjunctions is isolation or separation.

Literature review.

There are a number of researches conducted by different linguists among whom we find Baldrick, Chris (2008), Cobrett, Edward P.J and Connors, Robert J (1999), Babayev Javid (2023), Jhonson, Christopher, Hudson, David (2020), Mahony David (2003), Leengen, Marcus (2019), Zafarris, Jess (2017), Forsyth, Mark. (2014). They carried out some researches on hyperbole, meiosis, polysyndeton and many other rhetoric devices.

Methodology

Observations made in speech revealed interesting facts about the usage of frequency of stylistic devices with conjunctions. The observations were carried out on different sources including films, everyday speech, song lyrics and literature.

Figure 1.

The pie chart above describes the frequency of conjunction use with rhetoric devices. As seen from the pie chart, the most frequently used stylistic device is simile with 30% which is followed by paradiastole which makes up 25%. Hyperbole with 20% is used more often in ratio to polysyndeton and meiosis which accounted for 15% and 10% respectively. This pie chart was compiled according to a survey conducted with the observations in speech by the author.

Discussions and results

Excessive use of conjunctions such as 'and' makes up polysyndeton. Polysyndeton is the deliberate use of conjunctions in the sentence for the purpose of slowing up the rhythm of the prose so as to produce an impressively solemn note [3]. Eventually, it leads to emergence of pleonasm. Since the usage of conjunctions repeatedly seems to be meaningless. Ernest Hemingway uses polysyndeton in "After the storm". For example, I said, 'Who killed him?' and he said, 'I don't know who killed him but he's dead all right,' and it was dark and there was water standing in the street and no lights and windows broke and boats all up in the town and trees blown down and everything all blown and I got a skiff and went out and found my boat where I had her inside Mango Key and she was all right only she was full of water. Most sentences used in the example are simple and all are conjoint to each other with the conjunction "and".

It is possible to take an example for the usage of disjunction "or". We can see extensive use of 'or' in the excerpt from "The Voyage of the Dawn Trader"; And I do not see that it brings into the islands meat or bread or beer or wine or timber or cabbages or books or instruments of music or horses or armour or anything else worth having.

The disjunction 'nor' is also used in the literary works namely, in the "The lion in winter"; Oh, my piglets, we are the origins of war -not history's forces, nor the times, nor justice, nor the lack of it, nor causes, nor religions, nor ideas, nor kinds of government-not any other thing. We are the killers.

While polysyndeton emerges as a result of excessive use of conjunctions or disjunctions, syndeton is a normal use of a conjunction or disjunction. In syndeton, the speaker avoids needless extensive use of conjunctions or disjunctions. The speaker tries to use appropriate conjunction or disjunction in its place. For instance, I went to the shop to buy bread, sugar and salt.

Unlike polysyndeton and syndeton, asyndeton ignores the use of conjunctions or disjunctions in two or more successive sentences. The sentences are split from each other either with comma or full-stop or semi-colon. For example, I went to the shop to buy bread. Sugar. Salt.

Paradiastole appears as a result of disjunctions such as "neither...nor", "either...or", "not" and "nor" as disjunctions. Paradiastole is explained as "the rhetorical techniques of evaluative redescription-more popularly known as euphemism and dysphemism -designed to enlarge or reduce the moral significance of something" [8]. Unlike polysyndeton, paradiastole is might not be repeated between multiple successive sentences. Both paradiastole and polysyndeton are syntactical stylistic devices. The only difference between them is that polysyndeton is the deliberate repetition of conjunctions or disjunctions while paradiastole does not seek for such an aim. An appropriate sample for paradiastole is: "this agglomeration which was called and which still calls itself the Holy Roman Empire was neither holy, nor Roman, nor an empire"

Paradiastole consists in making the best of a bad thing: the technique consists in the euphemistic substitution of a negative word with something more positive. On the one hand, paradiastole resembles to litotes which is also called "meiosis" by mistaken. As obvious, litotes is positive representation of negation. On the other hand, paradiastole is euphemistic expression of dysphemism [5]. There is a co-fusion of two rhetoric devices here -dysphemism and litotes. This phenomenon can be taken for joint stylistic devices [4].

Henry Peacham considers paradiastole as a tool of excuse. The so-called rhetoric device is also observed with prepositions. For instance,

You should have seen how wisely I proceeded—with what caution – with what foresight—with what dissimulation I went to work.

Sometimes, conjunctions such as “as” and “like” form some certain stylistic devices. However, these conjunctions cannot create any rhetoric device in isolation. They can generate simile, meiosis, hyperbole in combination with nouns, adjectives and adverbs.

Simile is one of the frequently used rhetoric devices that emerges with the combination of conjunctions and adjectives. Adjectives are usually linked to nouns in the examples. Unlike metaphor, there is a direct transference in simile by means of the conjunctions “as” and “like”. However, transference is hidden in metaphor. Everything will be clear after we take an example for simile;

How can you go out in such weather? It is as hot as hell.

Her face became as white as a ghost when she spotted the thief in her house.

I like my new quilt, since it is as soft as velvet.

My grandpa’s mind is as sharp as a razor.

Some of these stylistic devices are ready-made phrases or idioms. Hence, most phrases and idioms can create simile in the meanwhile. Some phrases and idioms bear an abstract meaning while the others possess a real meaning.

The so-called conjunctions based on resemblance or transference may also form meiosis. In rhetoric, meiosis is considered to be a deliberate understatement. It is mainly used to belittle or undermine a person, subject or situation. For example,

The child was as tiny as an ant.

As we see, the child was deliberately made smaller, though the size of a child can never be as small as an ant. There is not always a need to use the conjunctions “as” and “like” while creating a meiosis. The transference can also be indirect as in metaphor. For example, the Atlantic ocean is sometimes called “The pond”. As seen, the second biggest ocean on the planet was diminished on purpose and resembled to a small pond. Hence, we deliberately diminished the size of the ocean without using any conjunctions [1]. Meiosis is sometimes used to form a euphemistic character [2].

Meiosis is accepted as the opposite of hyperbole. Hyperbole is used to exaggerate the meaning or size of a person, thing or situation. It is sometimes called “auxesis” in rhetoric. It is mainly employed to create emphasis or effect. In everyday speech, it has an intensifying function. For example,

He is as tall as a giraffe

I am as hungry as a bear

He is as heavy as an elephant

From above-mentioned examples, it turns out that the quality and the size of a person have deliberately been exaggerated. As in meiosis, there is also a co-existence of simile and hyperbole in the afore-mentioned examples. The concept of “Joint stylistic devices” also shows itself in above-mentioned examples.

As in meiosis, there is no need to use conjunctions in hyperboles every time. Hyperboles can also appear without conjunctions which have been shown with examples below;

She had a thousand missed calls on her phone.

I was so hungry, I was steaming at the ears.

As seen from the above-mentioned examples, there is also a metaphor in the sentences which is proven with indirect transference. Some phraseological units or set-expressions, even idioms can create hyperbole as in meiosis. This rhetorical device can be used for serious or ironic or comic effects [7]. Hyperbole expresses emotions and feelings from the speaker or from those who might talk about. It may be used in a form of humor, excitement, distress, and many other emotions, all depending on the context in which the speaker uses it [6].

Conclusion.

Overall, it should be noted that the article revealed the co-existence of some rhetorical devices in the same examples. Another novelty set forth by the author is the claim to classify the disjunctions as a separate part of speech in grammar. The fusion or co-existence of some rhetoric devices is seen in the examples taken for meiosis and hyperbole. Hence, metaphor and simile were also observed along with meiosis and hyperbole. It turned out that the conjunctions and disjunctions cannot form a rhetoric or stylistic device in isolation. They could form stylistic devices while combining with notional parts of speech such as nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs and numerals.

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